

Ways to Improve Cognitive Activity Based on the Structuring of the Methodological Training Process

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 30 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 03 Nov 2024; **Published:** 27 Dec 2024

Abstract: This scientific article provides detailed information on ways to improve cognitive activity based on the structuring of the methodological training process.

Keywords: Intellectual potential, methodological training, team learning technology, collaborative learning technology, problem-based learning technology, module technology.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the issues of improving cognitive activity in students based on the structuring of the methodological preparation process and introducing innovative approaches to their pedagogical activities are becoming relevant. Because if methodological preparation is thorough, it will be possible to achieve the quality of education and the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. Because, "the historical and spiritual factor that will be a solid support and support for the strategy of the new Uzbekistan, that is, our greatest wealth is the existence of the great cultural heritage and intellectual potential of our people. It is known that this scientific and spiritual heritage, widely recognized by the world community, has made an invaluable contribution to the development of world culture and spirituality. It is precisely this factor that is creating the foundation of the New Uzbekistan, the basis for the broad development of science, spiritual and cultural activities, and education and upbringing to a new level." In general, the promising civilization of any society depends on its educational status, the structure and essence of the new education system, and its deep educational culture. A high level of education is the only factor that ensures the future of the society, the state and the nation, and determines its influence in the world.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Methodological training is the ability to know, master, and apply in practice the forms, methods, and means of effectively organizing the educational process, to be able to qualitatively analyze and evaluate the results of activities, to study advanced international pedagogical experiences, to design and successfully implement the educational process.

If we consider the definition and scientific research that reveal the essence of the concept of "methodological training", the term "methodology" first appears in the Russian scientific literature in 1783 in the works of F.I. Yankovich.

The term preparation, in turn, is interpreted in the explanatory dictionary of S.I. Ozhegov and N.Yu. Shvedov as follows: 1) the study and formation of knowledge necessary for something; 2) knowledge acquired by a person. Thus, preparation is the educational process

and its result. In this case, training can be carried out for the purpose of educating a person or for his acquisition of a certain professional specialty. Achieving the first goal involves, first of all, the formation of a certain system of knowledge and personal characteristics. The second goal is often achieved through the formation of skills and qualifications necessary for the implementation of professional activities.

Russian scientist V.V. Malev classifies and defines the characteristic features of the modern methodological system as follows: “the need to plan the educational process on a scientific basis; achieving harmony and unity of theoretical and practical training; the ability to learn educational material at a fast pace and at a high level; achieving high activity and sufficient independent activity of students; ensuring the unity of individual and group activities; achieving full provision of the educational process with technical means; ensuring an integrated approach to the study of various subjects and subjects.

According to the researcher Sh. Ibragimova, methodological preparation means “methodically rational organization of the pedagogical process, correct determination of forms of educational or educational activity, ability to select methods and means in accordance with the purpose, effective application of methods, successful use of means. In addition, according to V. A. Adolf and V. A. Slastenin, methodological competence has a clearly expressed practical nature and, by its essence, reflects an expanded system of knowledge on specific issues of teaching a particular subject. This requires modernization of pedagogical processes. When improving the methodological preparation of future teachers, they are required to know the following educational technologies:

1. **Team, group teaching technology.** A group of people united on the basis of caring for each of their members, its main principles are: small groups, pairs, mutual learning in them; mutual control, mutual management. As a result of properly organized pedagogical leadership and management, the use of these forms creates conditions characteristic of a team, such as understanding a common goal, purposeful setting of tasks, interdependence and control.
2. **Person-oriented teaching technology.** An individual form of education that helps to reveal the individual characteristics of the student, develop his abilities, and form him as a person, taking into account his interests, is called person-oriented education.
3. **Cooperative teaching technology.** The main idea of cooperative teaching is not just to do something together, but to study together. The ability of students to master educational material is different: some quickly grasp the teacher's explanations, while others need additional time and practice. If students are divided into small groups of 4-5 people and each of them is clearly assigned a task, then in this situation each member of the group feels responsible for the task assigned to him and the group. Low-level learners ask for help from advanced learners. Problems that arise are solved in cooperation.
4. **Problem-based learning technology.** The essence of problem-based learning is to organize the management of students' cognitive activity in the acquisition of new knowledge by creating problem situations in their educational work and solving educational tasks, problems and questions. The task of problem-based learning is to cooperate with students in the effective acquisition of knowledge systems and methods of intellectual and practical activity, to form in them the skills of creative application of acquired knowledge in new situations, to develop cognitive independence and the solution of educational and educational problems. In the method of conducting training sessions based on problem-based teaching, creative, creative and heuristic, problem-based presentation of information, presentation of information through problem-based initiation are the main methods.

5. **Module technology.** The student receives a certain amount of independent knowledge based on the program recommended to him. A module is a completed unit of educational material developed on the basis of certain principles, aimed at studying one or several fundamental concepts of a subject. For the successful implementation of modular education, a modular program must comply with the following principles: targeted information materials. An information block is formed based on a clearly defined purpose of the topic; the relevance of complex, integrated and specific didactic goals. The use of module technology requires the preparation of an educational and methodological complex consisting of: test tasks that control students' knowledge; independent work tasks; educational and methodological handouts; a list of literature, a working curriculum.

In order to improve the cognitive activity of students based on the structuring of the methodological preparation process, it is necessary to achieve harmony in the formation of their general cultural potential, professional knowledge and personal qualities. Therefore, there is a need to integrate all knowledge subjects provided for in the curricula. Thus, integrated methodological activity is based on strengthening interdisciplinary connections in teaching. The importance of using new pedagogical technologies and interactive teaching methods in order to develop students' independent thinking and creative abilities in mastering subjects is great. Therefore, personalized education can be effective under the influence of cooperative pedagogy and methods of working in small groups. The widespread introduction of modern information communications in further increasing the effectiveness of educational technologies will give good results. The impact of innovative processes on social development is increasing day by day. At all times, knowledge has been highly valued by humanity, has been considered the basis for the development of intellectual abilities in society and man, and has served to increase the effectiveness of innovative methodological activity. Because, "the socio-economic life of developed countries shows that today the investment in knowledge is developing and takes priority over fixed assets.

It is not for nothing that in our country special attention is paid to improving the cognitive activity of students based on the structuring of the methodological training process. In recent years, on the basis of educational reforms, the issue of creating new generation textbooks for secondary schools, academic lyceums and higher educational institutions in the development of the material, technical and educational-methodological base is being positively resolved, and the establishment of the Fund for the Promotion of Scientific and Applied Research in the Field of Innovative Technologies under the Committee for the Development of Science and Technology of the Republic, as established in the program, is aimed at increasing the efficiency of this area.

Also, since methodological preparation is also a creative process, the activity of a creative teacher who creates something new and sets as his goal the achievement of its result also requires the manifestation of the values, knowledge and abilities inherent in his spiritual being. In the process of innovative methodological activity carried out individually by an individual, such potential is manifested as a set of socio-cultural values, as a person's individual qualities, knowledge, skills, qualifications and talents, and in the course of activity implemented on a collective or mass scale. Thus, for the effective implementation of new pedagogical activity by an individual creative person or by a creative team, the necessary spiritual potential must exist in the spiritual world of a person or in the form of socio-cultural systems, and there must be an opportunity to put this potential into action when the need arises.

We will separately consider the principles of preparing students for pedagogical activities developed on the basis of improving the system of cognitive activity. They consist of:

I. Strategic directions:

1. As a result of purposeful continuous education, each graduate should analyze and evaluate not only his knowledge, but also his ability to think and act, that is, the consequences of the corresponding development.
2. An important result of education is the development of a scientifically based multidimensional social consciousness of a person as an active and responsible subject of social life.
3. It should contribute to the formation of self-fulfillment of a person, create initial opportunities for life and create conditions for self-realization.
4. A citizen who has received education in pedagogy should competently solve not only the problems of social formation and social adaptation, but also the problems of social treatment, correction, and social rehabilitation of each person who has become the object of his attention.
5. Pedagogical education should become an integral part of any type of education.
6. An organic part of any education should be the development of positive social consciousness and the formation of social behavior on this basis.
7. It is necessary to respect the rights and dignity of every person, regardless of gender, nationality, religious belief, political affiliation, social status.
8. It is necessary to form a reliable foundation for providing an active attitude in the education of citizens both in terms of social policy issues and social life, based on the values of social well-being, freedom, justice and equality.
9. Purposeful formation of the reputation of a specialist working in the field of pedagogy.

II. Directions for operation:

1. Development includes the creation of complex educational content.
2. Building an educational process based on humanization and universal human values, the basic principles of respect should be based on the fact that the basic knowledge, skills and abilities of specialists have a general civil and personal nature.
3. It is important to rely on the creative synthesis of fundamental and technological, practical training.
4. To create conditions for students to acquire basic skills, to include general cultural and professional (social technologies, research, organizational, administrative, social-design, etc.) in lesson plans.
5. To take into account the phenomenon of the multiplicity of activities of a pedagogical specialist in the development of educational content (various functional tasks, categories of users of activity technologies and social services).
6. Regular exchange of information and research results among specialists preparing for pedagogical activities.
7. Organizing the process of supporting the professional self-awareness of students and graduates based on the principles of continuity and consistency.
8. Paying attention to the quality selection of the content of the educational program (determining the order of studying subjects, determining the didactic units of each subject, introducing an action-oriented paradigm of education, updating the subjects of the taught subjects in a timely manner, etc.).
9. Improvement of teaching-methodical complexes for teachers and students to learn the

subjects of the main education program.

10. Ensuring the content of the educational activity corresponds to the scientific achievements in the field of education and training.
11. In order to arouse interest in pedagogical activities, conducting active career orientation among young people within the framework of preparation for vocational training.
12. Attracting scientific and pedagogical personnel with specialized (social) education.
13. Encouraging the scientific activity of teachers, students and doctoral candidates.
14. Establishing a balance between theoretical and practical training.
15. Providing material and technical equipment (technical manuals, demonstration tools, etc.) quality assurance.
16. Smart and effective organization of control measures (tests, practical and state exams, etc.)
17. Critically understand the "evaluation policy" of teachers, develop uniform requirements for monitoring and evaluating students' knowledge.
18. Implementation of effective ways of organizing the educational process, active teaching methods and intensive teaching technologies (teaching technologies - modular, problem-based, dialogic, developmental, etc.). Teaching methods - effective use of innovation, discrete self-education, design, modeling, internship, testing, training, synectics, "round talk", polemic, debate and others.
19. Uniting the efforts of all consumers of educational services (interested parties) - teachers, administrative and management staff, students, parents, employers and others in preparing students for pedagogical activities.
20. To eliminate the diversity of educational concepts, to eliminate the cause of mutual understanding difficulties for both sides of educational institutions and social activities, to create local authorship programs.
21. Paying attention to the development of important professional qualities of students: social activity, community, tolerance, reflexivity, creativity and others.
22. Humanizing the content of continuous education is the separation of humanitarian knowledge that reflects the inner world of a person, his activity in the spiritual sphere.
23. Incorporation (integration) of the most advanced world education standards into the content and technologies of education.

Today, it was not enough for information technologies and devices to have their own characteristics to create real cognitive systems. The main shortcoming of such technologies, which have entered the teaching methods and technologies on a large scale, is that the intellectual actions performed by them are limited to the scope of the pre-developed program, there is no possibility to independently base the creative thought, and independently direct it to the final positive result. Therefore, it is up to the creative teacher to evaluate the results obtained from the use of information technologies and tools, and to make a decision on whether or not to use them in the creative pedagogical process. Of course, in the innovative pedagogical process, it is not possible to solve such issues by the teacher himself, to completely entrust them to intelligent machines. At the same time, there is a need to introduce the use of computer equipment and technologies with cognitive ability for a part of creative tasks through the creation of innovation and the independent use of intellectual capacity.

Creation of systems and structures capable of performing such tasks with cognitive capacity in 3 directions, firstly, a full assessment of the situations that arise in the creative process, development of information programs that allow to choose the optimal option for performing a new task, and secondly, creation of new generations of computer technology with great functional potential. , thirdly, it was held with the aim of direct integration of information technologies and communication tools into the creative or production process.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the model of improving students' cognitive activity based on the structuring of learning is based on the innovative principles of modern pedagogy aimed at the quality of education, which implies that the division of the pedagogical process into separate small parts and the achievement of consistency in their sequential implementation affect the quality of education.

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